

Nonholonomic Frames for Finsler Space with (α, β) -Metrics

Brijesh Kumar Tripathi¹, K.B.Pandey² and R.B. Tiwari³

1. Department of Mathematics, L.E. College, Morbi(Gujrat) 363642, India

2. Department of Mathematics, K.N.I.T., Sultanpur,U.P., 228118, India

3. Department of Mathematics, M.K.R.E.C.I.T., Ambedkar Nagar(U.P.), India

E-mail: brijeshkumatripathi4@gmail.com, kunjbiharipandey05@gmail.com, tiwarirambharat@yahoo.in

Abstract: The purpose of present paper to determine the two special Finsler spaces due to deformations of some special Finsler space with help of (α, β) -metrics. Consequently, we obtain the non-holonomic frame for the (α, β) -metrics, such as (I) $L = \left(\frac{\alpha^2}{\alpha-\beta}\right) \frac{\beta^2}{\alpha} = \frac{\alpha\beta^2}{(\alpha-\beta)}$ i.e. product of Matsumoto metric and Kropina metric and (II) $L = (\alpha + \beta) \frac{\beta^2}{\alpha} = \beta^2 + \frac{\beta^3}{\alpha}$ i.e. product of Randers metric and Kropina metric.

Key Words: Finsler Space, (α, β) -metrics, Randers metric, Kropina metric, Matsumoto metric, GL-metric, Non-holonomic Finsler frame.

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§1. Introduction

In 1982, P.R. Holland [1] and [2] studies a unified formalism that uses a nonholonomic frame on space time arising from consideration of a charged particle moving in an external electromagnetic field. In fact, R.S. Ingarden [3] was the first to point out that the Lorentz force law can be written in this case as geodesic equation on a Finsler space called Randers space. The author R.G. Beil [5], [6] have studied a gauge transformation viewed as a nonholonomic frame on the tangent bundle of a four dimensional base manifold. The geometry that follows from these considerations gives a unified approach to gravitation and gauge symmetries. In the present paper we have used the common Finsler idea to study the existence of a nonholonomic frame on the vertical sub bundle VTM of the tangent bundle of a base manifold M .

In this paper, the fundamental tensor field of a Finsler space might be considered as the deformations of two different special Finsler spaces from the (α, β) -metrics. Further we obtain corresponding frame for each of these two Finsler deformations. Consequently, a nonholonomic frame for a Finsler space with special (α, β) -metrics such as first is the product of Matsumoto metric[11] and kropina metric[11] and second is the product of Randers metric[11] and Kropina metric. This is an extension work of Ioan Bucataru and Radu Miron [10] and also second extension work of S.K. Narasimhamurthy [14].

Consider, $a_{ij}(x)$ the components of a Riemannian metric on the base manifold M , $a(x, y) >$

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0 and $b(x, y) \geq 0$ Two functions on TM and $B(x, y) = B_i(x, y)(dx^i)$ a vertical 1-form on TM. Then

$$g_{ij}(x, y) = a(x, y)a_{ij}(x) + b(x, y)B_i(x, y)B_j(x, y) \quad (1.1)$$

is a generalized Lagrange metric, called the Beil metric. The metric tensor g_{ij} is also known as a Beil deformation of the Riemannian metric a_{ij} . It has been studied and applied by R. Miron and R.K. Tavakol in General Relativity for $a(x, y) = \exp(2\sigma(x, y))$ and $b = 0$. The case $a(x, y) = 1$ with various choices of b and B_i was introduced and studied by R.G. Beil for constructing a new unified field theory [6].

§2. Preliminaries

An important class of Finsler spaces is the class of Finsler spaces with (α, β) -metrics [11]. The first Finsler spaces with (α, β) -metrics were introduced by the physicist G.Randers in 1940, are called Randers spaces [4]. Recently, R.G. Beil suggested a more general case and considered the class of Lagrange spaces with (α, β) -metric, which was discussed in [12]. A unified formalism which uses a nonholonomic frame on space time, a sort of plastic deformation, arising from consideration of a charged particle moving in an external electromagnetic field in the background space time viewed as a strained mechanism studied by P. R. Holland [1], [2]. If we do not ask for the function L to be homogeneous of order two with respect to the (α, β) variables, then we have a Lagrange space with (α, β) -metric. Next we defined some different Finsler space with (α, β) -metrics.

Definition 2.1 A Finsler space $F^n = (M, F(x, y))$ is called with (α, β) -metric if there exists a 2-homogeneous function L of two variables such that the Finsler metric $F : TM \rightarrow R$ is given by

$$F^2(x, y) = L(\alpha(x, y), \beta(x, y)), \quad (2.1)$$

where $\alpha^2(x, y) = a_{ij}(x)y^i y^j$, α is a Riemannian metric on the manifold M , and $\beta(x, y) = b_i(x)y^i$ is a 1-form on M .

Consider $g_{ij} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{(\partial^2 F^2)}{(\partial y^i \partial y^j)}$ the fundamental tensor of the Randers space (M, F) . Taking into account the homogeneity of a and F we have the following formulae:

$$\begin{aligned} p^i &= \frac{1}{a} y^i = a^{ij} \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial y^j}; & p_i &= a_{ij} p^j = \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial y^i}; \\ l^i &= \frac{1}{L} y^i = g^{ij} \frac{\partial l}{\partial y^j}; & l_i &= g_{ij} l^j = \frac{\partial L}{\partial y^i} = P_i + b_i, \\ l^i &= \frac{1}{L} p^i; & l^i l_i &= p^i p_i = 1; & l^i p_i &= \frac{\alpha}{L}; & p^i l_i &= \frac{L}{\alpha}; \\ & & b_i P^i &= \frac{\beta}{\alpha}; & b_i l^i &= \frac{\beta}{L} \end{aligned} \quad (2.2)$$

with respect to these notations, the metric tensors (α_{ij}) and (g_{ij}) are related by [13],

$$g_{ij}(x, y) = \frac{L}{\alpha} a_{ij} + b_i P_j + P_i b_j - \frac{\beta}{\alpha} p_i p_j = \frac{L}{\alpha} (a_{ij} - p_i p_j) + l_i l_j. \quad (2.3)$$

Theorem 2.1([10]) *For a Finsler space (M, F) consider the matrix with the entries:*

$$Y_i^j = \sqrt{\frac{\alpha}{L}} (\delta_j^i - l^i l_j) + \sqrt{\frac{\alpha}{L}} p^i p_j \quad (2.4)$$

defined on TM . Then $Y_j = Y_j^i (\frac{\partial}{\partial y^i})$, $j \in 1, 2, 3, \dots, n$ is a non holonomic frame.

Theorem 2.2([7]) *With respect to frame the holonomic components of the Finsler metric tensor $\alpha_{\alpha\beta}$ is the Randers metric g_{ij} , i.e.,*

$$g_{ij} = Y_i^\alpha Y_j^\beta \alpha_{\alpha\beta}. \quad (2.5)$$

Throughout this section we shall rise and lower indices only with the Riemannian metric $\alpha_{ij}(x)$ that is $y_i = \alpha_{ij} y^j$, $\beta^i = \alpha^{ij} \beta_j$, and so on. For a Finsler space with (α, β) -metric $F^2(x, y) = L(\alpha(x, y), \beta(x, y))$ we have the Finsler invariants [13]

$$\rho_1 = \frac{1}{2\alpha} \frac{\partial L}{\partial \alpha}; \rho_0 = \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial^2 L}{\partial \beta^2}; \rho_{-1} = \frac{1}{2\alpha} \frac{\partial^2 L}{\partial \alpha \partial \beta}; \rho_{-2} = \frac{1}{2\alpha^2} \left(\frac{\partial^2 L}{\partial \alpha^2} - \frac{1}{\alpha} \frac{\partial L}{\partial \alpha} \right) \quad (2.6)$$

where subscripts 1, 0, -1, -2 gives us the degree of homogeneity of these invariants.

For a Finsler space with metric we have,

$$\rho_{-1} \beta + \rho_{-2} \alpha^2 = 0 \quad (2.7)$$

With respect to the notations we have that the metric tensor g_{ij} of a Finsler space with (α, β) -metric is given by [13]

$$g_{ij}(x, y) = \rho \alpha_{ij}(x) + \rho_0 b_i(x) + \rho_{-1} (b_i(x) y_j + b_j(x) y_i) + \rho_{-2} y_i y_j. \quad (2.8)$$

From (2.8) we can see that g_{ij} is the result of two Finsler deformations

$$\begin{aligned} I. \quad a_{ij} &\rightarrow h_{ij} = \rho a_{ij} + \frac{1}{\rho_{-2}} (\rho_{-1} b_i + \rho_{-2} y_i) (\rho_{-1} b_j + \rho_{-2} y_j) \\ II. \quad h_{ij} &\rightarrow g_{ij} = h_{ij} + \frac{1}{\rho_{-2}} (\rho_0 \rho_{-1} - \rho_{-1}^2) b_i b_j. \end{aligned} \quad (2.9)$$

The nonholonomic Finsler frame that corresponding to the I^{st} deformation (2.9) is according to the Theorem 7.9.1 in [10], given by

$$X_j^i = \sqrt{\rho} \delta_j^i - \frac{1}{\beta^2} \left(\sqrt{\rho} + \sqrt{\rho + \frac{\beta^2}{\rho_{-2}}} \right) (\rho_{-1} b^i + \rho_{-2} y^i) (\rho_{-1} b_j + \rho_{-2} y_j), \quad (2.10)$$

where $B^2 = a_{ij}(\rho_{-1}b^i + \rho_{-2}y^i)(\rho_{-1}b_j + \rho_{-2}y_j) = \rho_{-1}^2b^2 + \beta\rho_{-1}\rho_{-2}$.

This metric tensor a_{ij} and h_{ij} are related by,

$$h_{ij} = X_i^k X_j^l a_{kl}. \quad (2.11)$$

Again the frame that corresponds to the II_{nd} deformation (2.9) given by,

$$Y_j^i = \delta_j^i - \frac{1}{C^2} \left(1 \pm \sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{\rho_{-2}C^2}{\rho_0\rho_{-2} - \rho_{-1}^2} \right)} \right) b^i b_j, \quad (2.12)$$

where $C^2 = h_{ij}b^i b^j = \rho b^2 + \frac{1}{\rho_{-2}}(\rho_{-2}b^2 + \rho_{-2}\beta)^2$.

The metric tensor h_{ij} and g_{ij} are related by the formula

$$g_{mn} = Y_m^i Y_n^j h_{ij}. \quad (2.13)$$

Theorem 2.3([10]) *Let $F^2(x, y) = L(\alpha(x, y), \beta(x, y))$ be the metric function of a Finsler space with (α, β) metric for which the condition (2.7) is true. Then*

$$V_j^i = X_k^i Y_j^k$$

is a nonholonomic Finsler frame with X_k^i and Y_j^k are given by (2.10) and (2.12) respectively.

§3. Nonholonomic Frames for Finsler Space with (α, β) -Metrics

In this section we consider two cases of non-holonomic Finsler frames with (α, β) -metrics, such a I^{st} Finsler frame product of Matusmoto metric and Kropina metric and II^{nd} Finsler frame product of Randers metric and Kropina metric.

(I) Nonholonomic Frames for $L = \left(\frac{\alpha^2}{\alpha - \beta} \right) \frac{\beta^2}{\alpha} = \frac{\alpha\beta^2}{\alpha - \beta}$

In the first case, for a Finsler space with the fundamental function

$$L = \left(\frac{\alpha^2}{\alpha - \beta} \right) \frac{\beta^2}{\alpha} = \frac{\alpha\beta^2}{\alpha - \beta},$$

the Finsler invariants (2.6) are given by

$$\begin{aligned} \rho_1 &= -\frac{\beta^3}{2\alpha(\alpha - \beta)^2}; \rho_0 = \frac{1}{2} \frac{(2\alpha^3 - \alpha\beta^2)}{(\alpha - \beta)^3}; \\ \rho_{-1} &= \frac{1}{2\alpha} \frac{\beta^2(\beta - 3\alpha)}{(\alpha - \beta)^3}; \rho_{-2} = \frac{\beta^3(3\alpha - \beta)}{2\alpha^3(\alpha - \beta)^3}; \\ B^2 &= \frac{\beta^2(1 - 3\alpha)^2b^2 + \beta^5(\alpha - \beta)(1 - 3\alpha)(3\alpha - \beta)}{4\alpha^4(\alpha - \beta)^6}. \end{aligned} \quad (3.1)$$

Using (3.1) in (2.10) we have,

$$X_j^i = \sqrt{-\frac{\beta^3}{2\alpha(\alpha-\beta)^2}} \delta_j^i - \frac{\beta^4}{4\alpha^4(\alpha-\beta)^5} \left[\sqrt{\frac{-\beta^3}{2\alpha}} + \sqrt{\frac{4\alpha^4(\alpha-\beta)^5 - \beta^4(3\alpha-\beta)}{2\alpha\beta(3\alpha-\beta)}} \right] \\ \times \left(b^i - \frac{(3\alpha-\beta)}{\alpha^2(\alpha-\beta)} y^i \right) \left(b_j - \frac{(3\alpha-\beta)}{\alpha^2(\alpha-\beta)} y_j \right). \quad (3.2)$$

Again using (3.1) in (2.12) we have,

$$Y_j^i = \delta_j^i - \frac{1}{C^2} \left(1 \pm \sqrt{1 + \frac{2(\alpha-\beta)^3 C^2}{\alpha^2(2\alpha-3\beta)}} \right) b^i b_j, \quad (3.3)$$

where $C^2 = -\frac{\beta^3}{2\alpha(\alpha-\beta)^2} b^2 + \frac{\beta(3\alpha-\beta)}{2\alpha^3(\alpha-\beta)^3} (\alpha^2 b^2 - \beta^2)^2$.

Theorem 3.1 Consider Finsler space $L = \left(\frac{\alpha^2}{\alpha-\beta} \right) \frac{\beta^2}{\alpha} = \frac{\alpha\beta^2}{\alpha-\beta}$, for which the condition (2.7) is true. Then

$$V_j^i = X_k^i Y_j^k$$

is non-holomic Finsler Frame with X_k^i and Y_j^k are given by (3.2) and (3.3) respectively.

(II) Nonholonomic Frames for $L = (\alpha + \beta) \left(\frac{\beta^2}{\alpha} \right) = \beta^2 + \frac{\beta^3}{\alpha}$

In the second case, for a Finsler space with the fundamental function $L = (\alpha + \beta) \left(\frac{\beta^2}{\alpha} \right)$ the Finsler invariants (2.6) are given by:

$$\rho_1 = -\frac{\beta^3}{2\alpha^3}; \rho_0 = \frac{3\beta + \alpha}{\alpha}; \rho_{-1} = -\frac{3\beta^2}{2\alpha^3}; \rho_{-2} = \frac{3\beta^3}{2\alpha^5}; \\ B^2 = \frac{9\beta^4}{4\alpha^8} (\alpha^2 b^2 - \beta^2), \quad (3.4)$$

$$X_j^i = \sqrt{-\frac{\beta^3}{2\alpha^3}} \delta_j^i - \frac{9\beta^2}{4\alpha^6} \left[\sqrt{-\frac{\beta^3}{2\alpha^3}} + \sqrt{-\frac{\beta^3}{2\alpha^3} + \frac{2\alpha^5}{3\beta}} \right] \left(b^i - \frac{\beta}{\alpha^2} y^i \right) \left(b_j - \frac{\beta}{\alpha^2} y_j \right). \quad (3.5)$$

Again using (3.4) in (2.12) we have

$$y_j^i = \delta_j^i - \frac{1}{c^2} \left[1 \pm \sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{2\alpha c^2}{2\alpha + 3\beta} \right)} \right] b^i b_j, \quad (3.6)$$

where $C^2 = -\frac{\beta^3}{2\alpha^3} b^2 + \frac{3\beta}{2\alpha^5} [\alpha^2 b^2 - \beta^2]^2$.

Theorem 3.2 Consider a Finsler space $L = (\alpha + \beta) \left(\frac{\beta^2}{\alpha} \right) = \beta^2 + \frac{\beta^3}{\alpha}$, for which the condition 2.7 is true. Then

$$V_j^i = X_k^i Y_j^k$$

is non-holomic Finsler Frame with X_k^i and Y_j^k are given by (3.5) and (3.6) respectively.

§4. Conclusions

Non-holonomic frame relates a semi-Riemannian metric (the Minkowski or the Lorentz metric) with an induced Finsler metric. Antonelli P.L., Bucataru I. ([7][8]), has been determined such a non-holonomic frame for two important classes of Finsler spaces that are dual in the sense of Randers and Kropina spaces [9]. As Randers and Kropina spaces are members of a bigger class of Finsler spaces, namely the Finsler spaces with (α, β) -metric, it appears a natural question: Does how many Finsler space with (α, β) -metrics have such a nonholonomic frame? The answer is yes, there are many Finsler space with (α, β) -metrics.

In this work, we consider the two special Finsler metrics and we determine the non-holonomic Finsler frames. Each of the frames we found here induces a Finsler connection on TM with torsion and no curvature. But, in Finsler geometry, there are many (α, β) -metrics, in future work we can determine the frames for them also.

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